

Europe is currently no superpower in computing, but it is never too late to become one.

The position of Europe in the world

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In order to set out a strategy for the future, it is important to know one's strengths and weaknesses. It also helps to identify opportunities, and to prepare for threats. Although Europe is currently no superpower in computing or in the business-to-consumer information and communication technology (B2C ICT) market, it is never too late to become one. For that to happen, it is important to understand the obstacles that make it difficult to grow global companies, and to develop policy to remove such barriers.

Key insights

- Europe's global economic impact is dwindling because other regions are growing faster due to their demographics, rapid economic development, or abundance of natural resources. The biggest long-term challenge for Europe is to sustain economic growth with a shrinking active population and growing costs for social security. Maintaining the current standard of living will require a highly educated and productive workforce.
- It is important for Europe to realize that computing is a key enabling technology of strategic importance because it is at the basis of all modern smart products and services. Europe should invest in the capacity to build its own computing solutions.
- Europe is a scientific powerhouse, but it fails to monetize some of its research results due to the lack of an entrepreneurial culture, venture capital and a sufficiently large ICT workforce.

Key recommendations

- The creation of well-funded international competence centres will help to retain and attract top talent, and to stay at the forefront of new digital technologies.
- Europe should continue to invest heavily in research and innovation, and in a more entrepreneurial Europe that generates lots of start-up, scale-up and global companies. Europe needs more venture capital to support the growth of scale-ups...
- Europe should invest in future-proof areas, such as the silver economy to support the ageing population (home automation, health, entertainment, ...) and technologies for sustainability (low power, the circular economy, ...). In terms of technology, hardware accelerators and artificial intelligence are key elements of future computing systems.

In this article, we present a SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, threats) analysis of the European computing systems ecosystem. We make a distinction between three stakeholders: (i)

publicly funded universities and research institutions ("Science and Technology"), (ii) the computing industry and its market, and (iii) the local and European governments responsible for creating an environ-

ment in which research, innovation and commercialization can take place ("Policy and Government"). Most data in this article comes from the European Commission report *Science, research and innovation performance of the EU 2022* [1].

Strengths and weaknesses

	Strengths	Weaknesses
Science and Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High-quality education • Excellent research • Growing academia-industry link • World leader in lithography for semiconductor manufacturing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong in research, but not in commercialization
Industry and Market	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Third largest market in the world • Stronger in systems than in components 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU ICT contributes less to GDP than in other advanced countries • Lack of venture capital culture • Lack of advanced foundries
Policy and Government	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Common market • Decent public funding level of research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of ICT workers • Fragmentation of funding

High-quality education

Europe has an excellent and affordable educational system from preschool to university. According to the 2023 *Times Higher Education World University Rankings* [2], more than one third of the top 100 universities are located in Europe. The US dominates the top 10 and the top 100, but all international rankings put Europe as the dominant continent in the top 500. This shows that Europe has a very solid higher education system.

Participation in higher education is growing in Europe, and there is still a lot of room for growth in some parts of Europe, see Figure 1.

A positive evolution is that the share of graduates of higher education in the science and technology sector is rapidly increasing too; see Figure 2.

Given demographic evolutions, Europe will not be able to match the number of higher education graduates of China in the future. There are only three ways to increase the number of graduates.

- Try to further increase participation, although there is not an unlimited number of students that are qualified to undertake higher education (Europe sets 40% as a target; some countries have already reached this level).

- Try to increase the number of graduates via lifelong learning. That means that workers are (re)trained while working, or between jobs.
- A final option would be to try to attract more foreign students/graduates, especially those who have plans to stay in Europe after graduation. Given the fact that almost every country in the world is trying to stop brain drain, and has created incentives to bring successful expats back to their home country, the impact of recruiting overseas students is also limited, and the numbers will always be lower than the number of local students.

Figure 1: Share of population aged 25-34 who have successfully completed tertiary studies

European universities generally do not have access to the huge endowments of some US universities, see Figure 3.

In the European Union (EU), the students pay on average about 20% of the real costs as tuition fees while in the United States and the UK it can be up to 66%. That makes higher education affordable for most young people in the EU. Especially during a recession, it also allows freedom of choice. Students do not have to worry how they are going to pay back student loans. This

is important for study programmes that do not lead to highly paid jobs, but are still societally very important (nursing, education, childcare, ...). Most EU students do not start their career in debt.

Excellent research

European universities produce significantly more PhD graduates per 1,000 of the population than American or Chinese universities, see Figure 4. The majority of European countries perform better than

the United States, even in science and technology.

During the last 20 years, Europe has maintained its global share of scientific publications, while the United States has seen a steady decline, and China has shown spectacular growth (Figure 5). Europe has not only retained its share of scientific publications, but also its share of the 10% most highly cited publications. The US is also losing its share of highly cited publica-

Figure 2: Share of higher education graduates employed in science and technology

Figure 3: Expenditure in tertiary education, 2018

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Figure 4: New doctoral graduates per 1000 population aged 25-34, 2017

Figure 5: World share in scientific publications and 10% highly cited scientific publications

tions. The same trend is visible for the top 1% highly cited publications.

It is remarkable that the sum of highly cited publications from the United States and China has been almost constant since 2000, which seems to indicate that Chinese presence is growing at the expense of the US. The explanation is that the US and China are competing in the same domain (technology), while the EU publications are focussing on different domains (arts, humanities, ...). If this trend continues, China will become the leader in publications and citations by the end of this decade. Hopefully, Europe will be able to defend its position in second place. As there is a correlation between the amount of public research funding and the number of highly cited publications, it seems crucial not to cut down on public research funding. The US and Japan have been cutting public research funding in the last decade, and their number of publications and citations have followed the same path.

Growing academia-industry link

Compared to the United States, Europe has now more public-private co-authored publications (Figure 6). This might be a result of the EU funding instruments

Figure 6: Public-private co-authored scientific publications in total scientific publications

in which universities and businesses are encouraged to collaborate. It is definitely a positive evolution.

World leader in lithography for semiconductor manufacturing

Europe has several research institutes and companies that are key players in semiconductor technology development (including ASML for making advanced EUV lithography machines, CEA, imec and Fraunhofer). They are Europe’s biggest asset when it comes to the further development of CMOS-technology, and their expertise might be crucial to the development of post-CMOS technology. This asset is very important because it means that Europe is at the table when important technology deals are being made.

The US and Europe want to become less dependent on foreign supply chains for their digital technology and want to create more domestic fabs. TSMC is investing in fabs all over the world, but so far not in Europe. Intel has already announced plans to build a fab in Europe.

Third largest market in the world

According to the International Monetary Fund, Europe (EU-27) has the third largest economy in the world (it lost its second place to China in 2021; see Figure 7). Obviously, Brexit has caused a serious reduction

in the GDP of the EU, but the economy of China is growing much faster than Europe’s.

Still, European businesses have access to a large internal market, with significant potential for growth in the new member states. Having access to a large internal market is an important advantage in times of troubled international trade relations. However, the European market is very fragmented due the diversity of regulations and languages across countries.

Stronger in systems than in components

In major embedded application domains, Europe is a global leader. According to the *Strategic Research Agenda for Electronic Components and Systems 2020* [3], Europe produces 25-30% of global annual value at the system level, compared to 13% at the component level (Figure 8, Figure 9). The system level is expected to grow tenfold between 2016 and 2025 while the component level will only double. The system level is a clear strength in Europe, and a strength that we should exploit. The

Figure 7: Top 3 biggest global economies

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Figure 8: Embedded application domain markets. (Source: ECS)

Figure 9: Worldwide electronics value chain in 2018. (Source: ECS)

sector that is particularly strong is transportation (automotive, air, rail).

Common market

At the policy level, one of the strengths is the common market, and the fact that Europe can act as one economic bloc in global trade negotiations. Individual countries do not have to negotiate individual agreements. However, there is still a long way to go before Europe becomes a fully integrated market with one set of laws, one currency and one tax system. The difference in minimum wages across Europe shows how pronounced the difference between countries is (Figure 10).

Strong public funding

Europe has a variety of research funding instruments, complementing national funding instruments. The research and innovation programmes of the European Commission help to stimulate research collaboration. European Research Council instruments support research excellence,

the flagship programmes aim to create critical mass in key research areas, the European Institute of Technology aims to stimulate research and innovation, and joint undertakings (JUs) like the Key Digital Technologies (KDT) JU, soon to become the Chips JU, aim to pool local and European funding to encourage cross-border research and innovation.

The total amount of public research and development (R&D) funding available makes Europe a good place to carry out R&D (at 0.73% of GDP). Worldwide, Europe is in second place after South Korea (Figure 11).

However, the relatively high amount of public funding across the EU does not compensate for the low R&D investments by industry (see weaknesses). When considered as a whole, Europe is dramatically lagging behind other regions of the world. The aim for Europe is to spend 3%

of GDP on R&D, but it is still far away from that target (Figure 12).

The intensity of R&D translates into the number of researchers employed. Although Europe produces a higher number of PhD graduates per 1,000 of the population than any other world region, this has not resulted in more researchers in employment. In addition, almost half of the researchers working in the EU are employed by the public sector (Figure 13).

Furthermore, there is great variation between European countries (Figure 14). There are frontrunners (first quadrant), and laggards (third quadrant).

Weaknesses

Strong in research, but not in commercialization

Europe is lagging behind Japan and at a comparable level with the US with respect to the innovation output indicator (based on four components: patents, employment

Figure 10: Minimum wages, January 2008 and 2017 (EUR per month) (Source: Eurostat)

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Figure 11: Evolution of public and Business R&D intensity 2019 (Source: DG Research and Innovation)

Figure 12: Evolution of total R&D intensity 1985-2019 (Source: DG Research and Innovation)

Figure 13: Total researchers (FTE) as % of total employment 2000-2018 (Source: DG Research and Innovation)

in knowledge-intensive activities, trade in knowledge-based goods and services, and the innovativeness of high-growth enterprises), see Figure 15.

On the other hand, in recent years several European cities have emerged as

start-up ecosystems. Regional and European authorities are currently investing heavily in the creation and the support of start-up ecosystems in all European urban areas. Globally, 37% of all newly created ecosystems are based in Europe (Figure 16).

ICT contributes less to GDP in the EU than in other advanced economies

The European ICT industry contributes around 4% to GDP, compared to more than 6% or more in competing world regions (Figure 17). One explanation is that Europe lacks major technology companies like

Figure 14: Public R&D intensity, 2018 and compound annual growth (%) 2007-2018 (Source: DG Research and Innovation)

Figure 15: Innovation output indicator (EU, 2011=100), 2020, 2021 (Source: DG Research and Innovation)

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Alphabet, Apple, Amazon, Meta or Microsoft (in the US) or Baidu, Alibaba, Tencent and Xiaomi (in China), as well as other major ICT companies like HP, Dell and IBM, and the ecosystem supporting them.

The lack of such large corporations can be explained by the lack of venture capital (VC) culture in Europe. In order for companies to grow to US\$50-100 million, they have to enter non-European capital markets like the United States or China. The US market is very competitive and sophisticated, and Asian markets are even more challenging. Even growing within Europe has its challenges, because Europe is not a

single entity, it is composed of a plurality of markets, languages, laws, cultures and so on. Therefore, it is difficult for a company to address the whole of Europe without extra work to adapt to each country. As an example, voice assistants appear later in non-English speaking countries due to the additional effort required to adapt them to different languages. Neither US or Chinese companies face such challenges.

The fact that Europe lacks major ICT companies has far-reaching consequences: it also means that venture capitalists are less eager to invest in European start-ups and scale-ups because there are fewer compa-

nies that might be able to acquire them. Companies that do grow significantly are often acquired by non-European companies: Nokia was acquired by Microsoft, Movidius and Yogitech by Intel, Silexica by Xilinx, for example. Fortunately, there are also counterexamples like Sysgo, which was acquired by Thales.

Non-European business leaders often articulate a clear vision of the future and tend to generate considerably more publicity than their European counterparts. While the personalities in question may vary, from the apparent instability of leaders like Elon Musk to the steady guidance

Figure 16: Share of emerging start-up ecosystems per world region (Source: DG Research and Innovation)

Figure 17: ICT sector value added share of GDP

of others like Lisa Su, what they have in common is frequent media coverage. In contrast, very few people know the CEOs of major European computing companies like Infineon, Ericsson and STMicroelectronics, who lack the glamour (or, in some cases, notoriety) associated with their international equivalents.

Lack of VC culture

More generally, Europe lacks a VC culture and, in this metric, the gap between the United States and Europe could not be bigger (Figure 18). This observation, in combination with the large number of young start-up companies, is problematic. It means that start-ups have to fight hard to get the funding to become a scale-up

company. Some of them turn to the US to get VC investments.

Fortunately, the majority of the investments that do take place are in the ICT sector (Figure 19).

Lack of advanced foundries

There used to be foundries in Europe, but they were acquired by non-European companies and disappeared. The fact that Europe depends on foreign foundries means that it has to import most of its semiconductors. The leading foundries are not located in low-wage countries, meaning that they did not leave Europe due to labour costs. Given the fact that Europe is a world leader in the development of the

technology used in foundries (CEA, imec, Fraunhofer, ASML), it is surprising that no large foundries are left in Europe and that Global Foundries some years ago decided to stop the development of 7nm technology and instead make its 14/12 nm FinFET platform more relevant to its customers.

One explanation is that European countries did not aggressively invest in new foundries (as was the case in South Korea and in Taiwan), and that European VCs are not interested in foundries (while they are in the United States). Another is that the European customers of the foundries like STM, NXP and Infineon are making products that do not require advanced processes because their market is micro-

Figure 18: Venture capitalist investments in the EU vs the US by development stage in 2020 (Source: DG Research and Innovation)

Figure 19: Venture capital investments in the EU per sector, 2021 (Source: DG Research and Innovation)

controllers instead of microprocessors, analogue devices versus memories.

To address this issue, the EU aims to create production capacity of 20% of the global chip market in Europe by 2030 to secure digital sovereignty, as part of the

Chips Act [17]. Recently, Intel announced plans to build a state-of-the-art foundry in Germany. TSMC might make a similar decision in the near future.

EU Chips Act and international public initiatives for semiconductors

On the 9 March 2021 the EU President von der Leyen announced the “European Digital Decade” and the associated “Digital Compass” [4, 5] stating the ambitions and targets of the EU policy for the digital transformation of our society and economy by 2030. The pandemic highlighted the central role of digital technologies in building and maintaining a successful and sustainable future. It also exposed the divide that still exists between areas in EU, as well as strategic weaknesses compared to some of the other world areas.

Among the objectives set, one concerns the semiconductor industry and aims at reaching a 20% market share of the semiconductor world market in value by 2030. As the current share is below 10% and the prediction for the market size is to double over the period, this implies at least a five-fold increase in production capabilities in EU. Moreover, the objectives include leading-edge technologies (below 5nm) where the current share of EU is 0%. Such ambitious targets cannot be attained without massive investments by EU industry and, given the current size and number of EU players, without large companies from outside EU investing here.

To support such massive investments, the EU Commission has proposed a new piece of legislation submitted for approval to the EU Parliament and the EU Council establishing a wide range of actions. This “European Chips Act” [6] proposal was presented on 8 February 2022 and is composed by a series of documents including a 36-article legislative text that was complemented, on 12 May, by a “Staff Working Document” [7] which provides a large number of details on the expected implementation.

The Chips Act is structured around three “Pillars”. Pillar 1 addresses the R&D effort necessary to maintain and improve technological capability in Europe and aims

at creating “Pilot Lines” and networked “Design Competence Centres” that could support the EU stakeholders in moving faster towards leading-edge technologies and inject innovations in the industry. Pillar 2 addresses the need for support to increase capacity in EU by establishing a fast track for the validation of national funding plans to “first of a kind” new fabrication facilities taking the EU beyond existing capabilities. Pillar 3 aims at creating an early warning and crisis management system to avoid industry shortages affecting critical EU sectors.

Currently, the outcome is still not clear (e.g. the ITRE Committee of the EU Parliament has recently published a list of over 100 proposed amendments [8] to the Chips Act) but the reactions are mixed. The accent on leading-edge technologies is questioned as it is seen as unreachable and outside the scope of the EU semiconductor industry, although EU industrial semiconductor tools suppliers see it as fundamental to maintain their leadership positions in some market segments (lithography, atomic layer deposition, ...). Bringing the fabrication facilities of non-EU players to Europe is seen by some as a drain on already limited public investment support and skilled labour force that would penalize EU players even if not in direct product competition.

Some member states do not see the benefit how the initiative would benefit them and are against the principle of public support for the semiconductor sector. At the other end of the scale, some stakeholders lament the low level of EU support (about €4 billion for Pillar 1) compared to similar actions in US, China and generally in Asia. The reliance on national funding for Pillar 2, which is likely to privilege national interests compared to more EU-wide needs of technology sovereignty and secure access to supply of chips, has also been raised as a concern.

In any case, just the announcement of the initiative has spurred a series of announcement of new facilities. Intel has announced plans to massively invest in Germany and Italy respectively on an advanced foundry facility (about €15 billion initially and up to €68 billion over 10 years) and advanced 3D and packaging (about €1.5 billion and up to €5 billion). These investments will be complemented by R&D, design and customer support investments in France, Spain and Poland. STMicroelectronics has announced an investment of nearly €700 million in Catania (Italy) on SiC production and the EU has already cleared €270 million of state aid for the endeavour. STMicroelectronics, Soitec and GlobalFoundries have announced a joint effort of about €1.5 billion in Crolles (France) on the FD-SOI ecosystem with both dedicated substrate production and a fab capable of producing up to one million 300mm wafers per year.

As a comparison, the US in their Chips Act have dedicated US\$53 billion of federal budget and US\$24 billion of tax credits to the semiconductor sector on top of the individual states’ initiatives. Of the US\$53 billion, US\$15 billion are dedicated to R&D initiatives very similar to the EU “Pilot Lines” and the existing 300mm infrastructures of imec, CEA and Fraunhofer in a clear attempt to repatriate some of the R&D currently done in EU by US industrial actors.

China published plans are of the order of US\$159 billion over 10 years with some of the larger regions (Shanghai, Beijing, Chengdu, ...) investing another US\$40 billion.

South Korea has launched a tax incentive to support US\$450 billion of industrial investments in R&D and manufacturing until 2030, while Japan only in the last year has allocated US\$5 billion to the sector and has signed contracts to support the installation of TSMC (one fab and one R&D centre) domestically.

Lack of ICT workers

Europe lacks hundreds of thousands of ICT workers. Fortunately, there is significant growth in the number of graduates (Figure 20), but the number of graduates does not yet match demand. It seems that Europe is not succeeding in convincing large enough numbers of high school students to start a career in the ICT sector. This is unfortunate because the competitiveness of this sector in Europe will depend on a sizeable workforce in order to innovate in big data analytics, artificial intelligence, robotics and so on.

Encouraging well-trained foreign workers to relocate to Europe en masse to help mitigate the shortage is not an effective solution. First, Europe needs more than one million ICT workers in the next decade. Secondly, the countries of origin try hard to keep local talent in their own countries. Finally, Europe has become less inviting to immigrants during the last decade. To complicate things further, foreign ICT workers will be attracted by well-paid jobs

in the major global innovation hubs, and it will be more difficult to convince them to accept a job in smaller cities, or in poorer countries.

The only long-term and sustainable solution is to invest heavily in the technical education of local people. In parallel, a set of highly visible European competence centres in strategic digital areas could (i) stop the brain drain of high-potentials for other world regions, and (ii) attract high-potentials from outside Europe.

Fragmentation of funding

The public funding system in Europe is highly fragmented. There are national funds, regional funds and European funds. There are funding instruments for applied research, for innovation, and for fundamental research. There are individual grants and collaborative research grants. A particular research proposal could fit multiple funding instruments and calls. Sometimes a research proposal can only be funded if different agencies agree to each

fund a part of the proposal. On top of all this, the success rate for research proposals is sometimes lower than 10%.

Within a funding agency, different committees deal with particular topic areas, which makes it very hard to secure funding for multidisciplinary project proposals because committees tend to give priority to the proposals that belong to the core of a topic area, leading to lower acceptance rates for interdisciplinary projects. It is therefore very hard for technologies that are common to several application domains, such as research in computing hardware and software, to be funded for their own intrinsic development. Instead, they must piggy-back on more domain-specific project calls. The organizational structure of the funding agency thus ends up constraining the research work that can be proposed in one single project. The fact that European Regional Development Fund has also started to be used to fund research only adds to the complexity.

Figure 20: Share and growth of tertiary graduates by field of study in the EU

Opportunities

Fortunately, there are also opportunities.

	Opportunities	Threats
Science and Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The end of Moore’s law 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic stagnation and shrinking work force • Brain drain
Market and Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Embedded systems, IoT, CPS, edge intelligence • Open source 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Saturating markets • Computing initiatives in countries such as China, Russia and Japan
Policy and Government	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solutions for societal challenges 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geopolitical instability

The end of Moore’s law

The increase of sequential performance at the pace of Moore’s law already ended a decade ago (end of Dennard’s scaling); parallelism kicked in to keep performance increasing in lockstep with number of transistors and cores, and now accelerators are the preferred technique to further improve performance, but the parallelism and the heterogeneity add a lot more complexity for software developers.

The design of accelerators marks a new era of architectural research to devise clever solutions to improve the performance per Watt in particular application area (graphics, cryptography, machine learning, ...).

There is however room (and also a need) for more disruptive solutions, possibly replacing the (rather inefficient) von Neumann architecture with other computing paradigms, but only if it is done with a high level of efficiency and in a short period of time. Progress in artificial intelligence could help in the efficient design of new systems.

Designing a new accelerator or launching a new technology will always be a daunting task as the proposed solution has to be better than current solutions, and also needs to have a roadmap in order to keep the lead.

Embedded systems, IoT, CPS, edge intelligence

The number one market opportunity in computing systems is the strongly growing market of secure edge computing (which encompasses the internet of things (IoT), cyber-physical systems (CPS), edge intelligence, automotive and industrial automa-

tion). Europe has the third largest economy in the world, it has a number of world-class players producing the key enabling technologies for advanced embedded systems, and it has strong automotive, health and industrial automation industries.

Furthermore, there are no non-European dominant companies like Alphabet, Amazon, Apple, Meta or Microsoft in this space yet and Europe is quite strong in . The stars in this domain will probably not be the same as those of the internet era (which are different from those of the mainframe era). Could the company dominating computing in 2030 be European? The only way to win this race is to invest in Europe’s strengths, support them to scale up, and hope that they will become world leaders.

Open source

Open source can help promote digital autonomy by removing the reliance on (mostly non-European) proprietary ICT solutions. Instead, open source relies on skills, which gives Europe, with its excellent higher education system, an advantage.

Moreover, as a key driver of innovation, open source may allow researchers to help European companies leapfrog over the incumbent players to become leaders in a specific field. As an example, recently there has been significant investment in the RISC-V open-source instruction set architecture at both the EU and member-state level. RISC-V has the potential of allowing Europe to compete in markets which for years have been dominated by non-EU companies, such as high-performance computing.

Given the lack of major vertical technology companies in Europe, the way for European companies to survive is usually to collaborate. Open source allows them to do this and, eventually, can give their technology a dominant position on the market; see for example Bosch’s AUTOSAR project in the automotive sphere. See [18] for a full discussion of the potential of open source to give Europe a competitive edge.

Solutions for societal challenges

Societal challenges form a huge opportunity for the European computing industry. Europe is the region with the highest number of people aged 60 or older [14]. The old age dependency ratio (OADR) is the number of 65+ people per 100 people of working age (24-64). That ratio will increase dramatically over the next 30 years (Figure 21). That means that, globally, Europe will have to search for solutions for the ageing population first. Since the rest of the world will face the same challenges in the future, Europe has an opportunity to develop and commercialize services and products for the silver economy first and sell them to the rest of the world.

The same reasoning holds for the environment. The European population (together with the US) has one of the largest ecological footprints in the world. Reducing the ecological footprint will become one of most important global challenges of the rest of the century. The European Green Deal will help European scientists and industry to find solutions for footprint reduction that can be used and applied across the world. This is a once in a lifetime opportunity.

At this point, Europe is the global leader in publications and patents in the domains

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of climate action, environment, and renewable energy. The opportunity (and challenge) for Europe is to exploit and monetize all this technological knowledge, and build a handful of global companies in the green tech domain. Europe has the potential to lead in this area, but it should make use of this window of opportunity, and not wait until it closes.

Overall, Europe could position itself as a provider of “quality” ICT which does not merely take monetary imperatives into account, but also meets “European” standards. Combined with regulation of access to the EU single market, this could prove a powerful way to boost European strengths. As an example, Europe could build on its strengths in cybersecurity to create a “kite

mark” standard for security in electronic devices and systems, and ensure that only products meeting the standards can be sold within the EU, as suggested by [19].

Figure 21: Percentage of 65+ people depending on 100 people of working age (old age dependency ratio) (Source: United Nations (2019))

Figure 22: Real GDP growth 2006-2016 (% change compared with previous years) (Source: Eurostat)

Threats

Economic stagnation and shrinking work force

Europe has been characterized by low economic growth over the past decade (Figure 22).

This situation has recently been aggravated by the economic impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. Then came supply chain problems in many sectors, the effects of the Brexit, and the energy crisis due

to the Ukrainian war. In the background, there is the increasing cost of supporting the ageing population. The cost of pensions will continue to grow until 2040 (when “baby boomers” will have reached their life expectancy).

An often forgotten corollary of the ageing population is the shrinking work-force. Figure 23 shows the number of people entering the job market per year (aged 21), and leaving the job market (aged

65). Until 2018, there were more people entering the job market (as many as five million in 2008, which is only 15 years ago). From now until 2040, Europe will lose one million active professionals per year, and this will continue for the next 20 years. After 2040, it will even increase. Europe has a labour force of about 200 million (70% of the working age population aged 20 – 64 (which is 57% of total population)). A reduction of one million per year means that 0.5% of the workforce will leave

Figure 23: Evolution of the size of the European job market

Figure 24: Population change by component (annual crude rates), EU-28, 1960-2016 (per 1.000 people)

the job market per year. Per 200 seasoned doctors, teachers, researchers, nurses, only 199 can be replaced by junior profiles. This leads to a war for talent, and increasing salary costs. We are seeing the first signs all over Europe. However, it is also important to note that 0.5% is the average for Europe. In some countries in Eastern Europe, the situation is much more dramatic in that for every 200 doctors, teachers, researcher, only 150 can be replaced. For these countries it is almost impossible to grow the economy due to the lack of workers.

Brain drain

There is a lot of public attention given to the topic of immigration in Europe. It is indeed the case that immigration has increased since the fall of the Berlin Wall

in 1989 and is now a major source of population growth in Europe (Figure 24).

This graph, however, masks the fact that net immigration is the difference between immigration and emigration. Emigration usually takes place from economically weaker countries toward economically stronger countries: from the Middle East and North Africa to Europe, from Eastern and Southern Europe to North-Western Europe, but also from North-Western Europe to the United States and other rich countries in the world.

In the research domain, there are countries who have succeeded in reversing the brain drain (the green countries in Figure 25). These countries are attractive because they offer good career perspectives for

researchers who want to move to Europe (funding, but also the ecosystem in which they will operate). Southern and Eastern Europe has not been successful in creating the right environment.

In computing, there seems to be a brain drain from Europe to the US. Top researchers and ambitious entrepreneurs are attracted by the merit-based American society and top salaries for high-potential candidates in both academia and industry. Large multinational ICT companies are attractive employers for young European talent eager to travel the world and make a fast career. Even if they do not want to move, US-based companies often acquire European companies in order to have access to their talent or to open subsidiaries in Europe. This is a less visible form of

Figure 25: Map of inflow and outflow of researchers

brain drain. Particularly in machine learning, there has been a very strong pull on the top talent in Europe by companies like Meta and Alphabet.

Europe should create attractive research ecosystems in order to attract top talent from outside Europe. It could create large and well-funded competence centres to retain European talent, and to attract excellent workers from abroad. CERN is a good example of such a competence centre, attracting talent from all over the world. The proposals for pan-European centres in artificial intelligence [11] and cybersecurity [12] launched recently will hopefully help fulfil this need.

Saturating markets

The market for desktop computers and laptops is shrinking, and the market for smartphones and tablets is shrinking too (after having cannibalized the markets of other devices like navigation systems, cameras, music and video players). The reason is that we have reached human scale: most people in the Western world already have all the devices they need, and the features of most devices have stabilized, eliminating the need to replace devices to get access to more features. The COVID-19 pandemic and the requirement to work and study from home might have created a short peak in the demand for devices needed to telework (mobile devices, head-

sets, webcams), but this is not a long-term trend.

A greater consciousness of the need to live more sustainable lifestyles is also encouraging people to use devices until the end of their lifetimes, or have them repaired if they are still usable. This will further reduce demand in the longer term. Fewer sales mean fewer resources to spend on the development of new devices and new features. This is not good news for major global B2C companies, but it could create an opportunity for Europe, which in any case is not strong in the B2C sector.

At this point, it seems that investments in energy savings have the best return-on-investment (e-mobility, photovoltaic systems, heat pumps, ...) and it is to be expected that these markets will be booming in the coming decade. They are full of digital technology, and Europe could focus on producing components and systems for these applications.

Computing initiatives in countries such as China, Russia and Japan

A threat to the European computing industry is the rapid development of the computing industry in other world regions. Many countries understand that computing is a key enabling technology of strategic importance, and are investing in their own research, products and companies. If Europe fails to do the same, it might even-

tually become dependent on technology that is designed, developed, produced and controlled outside Europe. The same holds for cybersecurity solutions.

The fastest growing country of the moment is China. There are several sectors where it has the ambition to become a world leader (artificial intelligence [16] and renewable energy being just two examples). This is evident from the quickly growing number of patent applications by Chinese companies, see Figure 26.

The ambition of China to become the frontrunner in artificial intelligence was made very clear in 2017 in their Next Generation Artificial Intelligence Development Plan [13]. It states: "... by 2030, China's AI theories, technologies, and applications should achieve world-leading levels, making China the world's primary AI innovation centre, achieving visible results in intelligent economy and intelligent society applications, and laying an important foundation for becoming a leading innovation-style nation and an economic power". China created a five-year AI talent training programme, and invested more than US\$2 billion in a huge AI industrial park in the suburbs of Beijing. The presence of Baidu, Alibaba and Tencent is an asset in developing advanced AI applications. The fact that US administrations have put restrictions on Chinese companies will not change this.

Figure 26: World share (%) of PCT patent applications 2000-2018 Source: OECD ((Patents by technology))

Geopolitical instability

Another threat is the geopolitical instability that Europe and the rest of the world are currently experiencing. After Brexit came the war in Ukraine, and the energy crisis in its wake. The US is tightening its grip on the Chinese tech industry. Meanwhile, the Chinese leadership are showing a renewed interest in Taiwan. According to Bloomberg, a Chinese invasion in Taiwan and the loss of the TSMC factories would lead to a global recession of US\$1 trillion [4]. Most countries are therefore trying to move part of the production of the chips they need closer to home [10].

Conclusion

Europe has traditionally struggled to transform its well-established, advanced research capacity into significant economic growth. However, with a potentially global shift to a mindset where the sky is no longer the limit, Europe can capitalize upon its strengths by prioritizing quality electronics for sustainable development, promoting company collaboration to pool resources and focusing on key verticals in which the continent is strong.

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